

Supplementary Information

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1. Experimental and Theoretical details

Equipment

All commercial chemicals, reagents and solvents were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich (Merck), TCI, Fluka and Penta and were used as received. Solvents were evaporated on Heidolph Laborta 4001 rotary evaporator. Column chromatography was carried out with silica gel 60 (particle size 0.040–0.063 mm, 230–400 mesh; Merck) and commercially available solvents. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was conducted on aluminium sheets coated with silica gel 60 F254, obtained from Merck, with visualization by a UV lamp (254 or 360 nm). ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded at 500 and 125 MHz, respectively, with a Bruker Ascend TM 500 at 20 °C. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm relative to the signal of $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Si}$. The residual solvent signal in the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra was used as an internal reference (CDCl_3 $\delta = 7.24$ and 77.00 ppm). Apparent resonance multiplicities are described as s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet) and m (multiplet), coupling constants (J) are given in Hz. The delay time for ^{13}C NMR APT spectra was 2 seconds. The E/Z molar ratios in the PSSs were calculated from the ^1H NMR integrals of $N\text{-CH}_3$ signals belonging to the particular (E)- and (Z)-isomers. Mass spectra were recorded on a GC/EI-MS configuration composed of an Agilent Technologies 7890B gas chromatograph (columns HP-5 ms Ultra Inert $30\text{ m} \times 0.25\text{ mm} \times 0.25\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and DB-35 ms Ultra Inert $30\text{ m} \times 0.25\text{ mm} \times 0.25\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ equipped with a 5977B MS detector (EI 70 eV, mass range 10–1050 Da). High-resolution MALDI MS spectra were measured with a MALDI mass spectrometer LTQ Orbitrap XL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) equipped with nitrogen UV laser (337 nm, 60 Hz). The LTQ Orbitrap instrument was operated in positive-ion mode over a normal mass range (m/z 50–2000) with resolution 100 000 at $m/z = 400$. The survey crystal positioning system (survey CPS) was set for the random choice of shot position by automatic crystal recognition. *Trans*-2-[3-(4-*tert*-butylphenyl)-2-methyl-2-propenylidene]malononitrile (DCTB) was used as a matrix. Mass spectra were averaged over the whole MS record for all measured samples. Thermal behaviour of the target compounds was measured in open aluminous (DSC) or alumina (TGA) crucibles under N_2 inert atmosphere with a scan rate of 5 °C/min within the range 25–400 °C (DSC) or with a scan rate of 3 °C/min within the range 25–400 °C (TGA). TGA was carried out using a Mettler-Toledo STAR^e System TGA 2 equipped with a horizontal furnace LF (400 W, 1100 °C), balance XP5 (resolution 1 μg) and cooling system HUBER Minichiller 600. The initial sample weight was approximately 7 mg. DSC was measured with a Mettler-Toledo STAR^e System DSC 2/700 equipped with FRS 6 ceramic sensor and cooling system

(HUBER TC100-MT). Electrochemical measurements were carried out in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ in a three-electrode cell by cyclic voltammetry (CV). The working electrode was glassy carbon disk (1 mm in diameter). As the reference and auxiliary electrodes were used leakless Ag/AgCl electrode (SSCE) containing filling electrolyte (3.4 M KCl) and titanium rod with a thick coating of platinum, respectively. Voltammetric measurements were performed by using an integrated potentiostat system ER466 (eDAQ Europe) operated with EChem Electrochemistry software. Potential window of the aforementioned electrolyte ranges between -2.0 to +2.0 V vs. SSCE. All peak potentials of the first oxidation and reduction are given vs. silver chloride electrode (SSCE; +0.205 V vs. SHE) as well. Absorption spectra were measured on a Duetta™ HORIBA spectrophotometer in 1,2-dichloroethane at 20 °C ($c \approx 5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$). The photoisomerization was induced using DUV-HL18W (340 nm), XRL-400-5E (400 nm), LED450-01 (450 nm), RLS-B465 (465 nm), G58A5111P (525 nm) LEDs supplied from a Roithner LaserTechnik and OSV6YL56A1A (415 nm), OSUB5111A-RS (470 nm) supplied from a Optosupply. The device for irradiation was constructed from 1.5 V AA battery, LLP20 current driver (Roithner LaserTechnik) and one or four parallelly-connected LEDs for UV-Vis or NMR methods. The device for irradiation with one embedded 340 nm LED DUV-HL18W was constructed from 9 V 6F22 battery and 270 Ω , 0.25 W resistor (Royal Ohm). The X-ray analysis was carried out with a Bruker D8-Venture diffractometer equipped with Mo (Mo/K α radiation; $\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) microfocus X-ray (I μ S) sources, Photon CMOS detector and Oxford Cryosystems cooling device.

HRS measurements were performed using a homemade setup that has been extensively described in previous papers.^[54,57,58] The experiments were done in diluted chloroform solutions with concentrations ranging from 10^{-2} to 10^{-3} mol/L. An amorphous quartz cuvette (of 3x3 mm² section) with 3 mm of optical path for the incident laser, and *ca.* 1.5 mm of optical path was used. Molecular first hyperpolarizabilities were determined from the intensity of the incoherent scattered light at the second harmonic (SH) frequency from the idler signal of a tunable Optical Parametric Generator (OPG) at 1300 nm. The main experimental quantities that are discussed in this study are the HRS hyperpolarizability (β_{HRS}), which is related to the magnitude of the SH signal, and the associated depolarization ratio (DR), which provides information on the symmetry of the molecular second harmonic scatterer. More details on these quantities and on their acquisition are reported in SI. All reported β values are given in atomic units (1 a.u. of $\beta = 3.6213 \text{ m}^4 \text{ V}^{-1} = 3.2063 \times 10^{-53} \text{ C}^3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ J}^{-2} = 8.641 \times 10^{-33} \text{ esu}$) according to the T convention of Ref.^[59]

DFT Calculations

The geometry of all possible conformers of each compound was optimized using density functional theory (DFT) with the ω B97X-D exchange-correlation functional (XCF)^[60] in association with the 6-311G(d) Gaussian basis set. The ω B97X-D XCF includes empirical corrections to describe London dispersion interactions, which were shown to be necessary to accurately describe the relative energies between (*E*)- and (*Z*)-isomers in azo-photoswitches.^[30,61] All optimized geometries were confirmed to be real minima by subsequent harmonic frequency calculations. Vertical absorption properties were computed at the M06/6-311+G(d) level, whereas second-order NLO responses were computed at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level. Several previous works demonstrated that the M06-2X XCF, which includes a double amount of exact Hartree-Fock exchange compared to M06, is reliable for calculating the first hyperpolarizabilities of conjugated dyes, including azo-compounds.^[39,54,62,63] Solvent effects were included in both geometry optimization and computation of optical properties by means of the integral equation formalism of the polarized continuum model (IEF-PCM).^[64] The solvent was chosen according to the one used in the corresponding experiment. The statistical populations of the various conformers of every target compound were determined based on their relative Gibbs energies according to a Boltzmann distribution using standard temperature ($T = 298.15$ K) and pressure ($P = 1$ bar) conditions. Molecular properties were then deduced by weighting the contribution of each conformer by its statistical population (see details in SI).

Synthesis

2-(5,5-Dimethyl-1,3-dioxan-2-yl)-1-methyl-1H-pyrrole (5):

N-Methylpyrrole-2-carbaldehyde **4** (500 mg, 1 eq., 4.58 mmol) was dissolved in toluene (70 ml). 2,2-Dimethyl-1,3-propanediol (955 mg, 2 eq., 9.17 mmol) and 4-methylbenzenesulfonic acid (43 mg, 0.05 eq., 0.23 mmol) were added. The reaction was refluxed at 165 °C for 4 hours using Dean-Stark apparatus. Then, the reaction mixture was cooled to 25 °C and diluted with saturated water solution of sodium bicarbonate (70 ml). Toluene was evaporated *in vacuo* and residual water phase was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 50 ml). The combined organic layers were dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and the solvent was evaporated *in vacuo*. The crude product was purified by flash chromatography (silica gel, hexane/ethyl acetate, 10:1). Colourless liquid. Yield 268 mg (30%) $R_f = 0.44$ (silica gel, hexane/ethyl acetate, 10:1). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 20 °C, 500 MHz): $\delta = 0.78$ (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.29 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.59 (d, 2H, $J = 11.0$ Hz, *O*-CH₂), 3.74 (d, 2H, $J = 11.5$ Hz,

O-CH₂), 3.76 (s, 3H, *N*-CH₃), 5.41 (s, 1H, *O*-CH), 6.02 (t, 1H, *J* = 3.0 Hz, CH), 6.20–6.21 (m, 1H, CH), 6.55 (t, 1H, *J* = 2 Hz, CH) ppm. MS-EI (70 eV): *m/z* = 195 ([M⁺], 39%), 126 (3), 109 (100), 80 (9), 53 (6).

General Procedure for Diazotization and Azo-coupling

A substituted aniline **6** (1 eq., 1.24 mmol) was dissolved in acetone (3 ml). Hydrochloric acid (18% in distilled water, 1.5 ml) was added and the reaction mixture was cooled to 0 °C. Sodium nitrite (1.2 eq., 1.49 mmol) dissolved in distilled water (1 ml) and cooled to 0 °C was added dropwise to the solution of aniline **6** and the reaction mixture was stirred for 10 minutes at 0 °C. Into a solution of *N*-methylpyrrole derivative **5** (1 eq., 1.24 mmol) and sodium carbonate (3 eq., 3.72 mmol) in acetone and water (15 ml, 1:1) cooled to 0 °C, the solution of prepared diazonium salt was added dropwise, the reaction mixture was allowed to warm to 25 °C, and was stirred for 1 hour. Acetone was evaporated *in vacuo* and the residual water phase was diluted with concentrated aqueous solution of ammonium chloride until neutral pH. The product was extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 20 ml), the combined organic layers were dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered, and the solvent was evaporated *in vacuo*.

General Procedure for Deprotection

An appropriate acetal **2** (1 eq., 5.87 mmol) was dissolved in the mixture of acetone and water (22 ml 10:1) and 4-methylbenzenesulfonic acid (0.1 eq., 0.59 mmol) was added. The reaction was refluxed at 90 °C for 2 hours. Acetone was evaporated *in vacuo*, the residual water phase was diluted with saturated aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate (10 ml), and extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 10 ml). The combined organic layers were dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered, and the solvent was evaporated *in vacuo*.

General Procedure for Knoevenagel Condensation

An appropriate azo-compound **1** (1 eq., 0.39 mmol) and malononitrile (1.5 eq., 0.59 mmol) were dissolved in dichloromethane (20 ml). Piperidine (0.1 eq., 0.0392 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min. at 25 °C. The reaction mixture was diluted with saturated aqueous solution of ammonium chloride and the crude product was extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 20 ml). The combined organic layers were dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered, and the solvent was evaporated *in vacuo*.

Azo-compound (1a): The title compound was synthesized from **2a** (2002 mg) following the general procedure for deprotection. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane) and recrystallized from dichloromethane/hexane. Red solid. Yield 1228 mg (82%). M.p. = 163 °C. *R_f* = 0.15 (silica gel, dichloromethane). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃,

20 °C, 500 MHz): δ = 2.65 (s, 3H, CH₃), 4.31 (s, 3H, *N*-CH₃), 6.73 (d, 1H, *J* = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.00 (d, 1H, *J* = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.93 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2 × CH), 8.07 (d, 2H, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 2 × CH), 9.72 (s, 1H, CHO) ppm. ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 26.85, 32.21, 100.17, 122.87, 123.13, 129.42, 133.92, 138.45, 150.70, 155.59, 181.10, 197.31 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) *m/z*: calculated for C₁₄H₁₄N₃O₂ ([M + H]⁺): 256.10805, found: 256.10764.

Azo-compound (1b): The title compound was synthesized from **2b** (2002 mg) following the general procedure for deprotection. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane) and recrystallized from dichloromethane/hexane. Orange solid. Yield 1198 mg (80%). M.p. = 147 °C. *R_f* = 0.04 (silica gel, dichloromethane). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 20 °C, 500 MHz): δ = 2.67 (s, 3H, CH₃), 4.32 (s, 3H, *N*-CH₃), 6.71 (d, 1H, *J* = 4.5 Hz, CH), 6.99 (d, 1H, *J* = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.58–7.61 (m, 1H, CH), 8.04–8.06 (m, 2H, 2 × CH), 8.42–8.43 (m, 1H, CH), 9.71 (s, 1H, CHO) ppm. ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 26.82, 32.22, 99.92, 123.15, 123.27, 126.29, 129.51, 130.58, 133.63, 138.18, 150.50, 153.25, 181.02, 197.39 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) *m/z*: calculated for C₁₄H₁₄N₃O₂ ([M + H]⁺): 256.10805, found 256.10778.

Azo-compound (1c): The title compound was synthesized from **2c** (2155 mg) following the general procedure for deprotection. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane) and recrystallized from hexane. Red solid. Yield 825 mg (50%). M.p. = 122 °C. *R_f* = 0.64 (silica gel, dichloromethane). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 20 °C, 500 MHz): 4.31 (s, 3H, *N*-CH₃), 6.73 (d, 1H, *J* = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.00 (d, 1H, *J* = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.74 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2 × CH), 7.95 (d, 2H, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2 × CH), 9.72 (s, 1H, CHO) ppm. ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 32.19, 100.18, 122.93, 123.08, 123.81 (q, *J_{C-F}* = 268.75 Hz), 126.37 (q, *J_{C-F}* = 3.75 Hz), 132.34 (q, *J_{C-F}* = 32.50 Hz), 133.91, 150.48, 154.93, 181.12 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) *m/z*: calculated for C₁₃H₁₀F₃N₃ (M⁺): 281.07705, found 281.07692.

Azo-compound (1d): The title compound was synthesized from **2d** (2155 mg) following the general procedure for deprotection. The crude product was purified by recrystallization from hexane. Orange solid. Yield 1023 mg (62%). M.p. = 136 °C. *R_f* = 0.28 (silica gel, dichloromethane). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 20 °C, 500 MHz): 4.31 (s, 3H, *N*-CH₃), 6.72 (d, 1H, *J* = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.00 (d, 1H, *J* = 5.0 Hz, CH), 7.61–7.64 (m, 1H, CH), 7.70–7.71 (m, 1H, CH), 8.04–8.05 (m, 1H, CH), 8.11 (s, 1H, CH), 9.72 (s, 1H, CHO) ppm. ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 32.23, 100.12, 119.60 (q, *J_{C-F}* = 3.75 Hz), 123.12, 123.74 (q, *J_{C-F}* = 270

(Hz), 125.89, 127.44 (q, $J_{C-F} = 3.75$ Hz), 129.79, 131.82 (q, $J_{C-F} = 32.50$ Hz), 133.79, 150.41, 153.09, 181.09 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $C_{13}H_{10}F_3N_3$ (M^+): 281.07705, found 281.07694.

Azo-compound (1e): The title compound was synthesized from **2e** (2495 mg) following the general procedure for deprotection. The crude product was purified by recrystallization from hexane. Red solid. Yield 1413 mg (71%). M.p. = 129 °C. $R_f = 0.41$ (silica gel, hexane/ethyl acetate, 5:1). 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 20 °C, 500 MHz): 4.31 (s, 3H, $N-CH_3$), 6.74 (d, 1H, $J = 4.5$ Hz, CH), 7.00 (d, 1H, $J = 4.5$ Hz, CH), 7.87–7.92 (m, 4H, $4 \times CH$), 9.74 (s, 1H, CHO) ppm. ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$, APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): $\delta = 32.21, 100.42, 122.68, 123.04, 127.09$ – 127.20 (m), 134.12, 150.46, 154.10, 154.10–155.11 (m), 181.18 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $C_{12}H_{11}F_5N_3OS$ ($[M+H]^+$): 340.05375, found 340.05368.

Azo-compound (1f): The title compound was synthesized from **2f** (2495 mg) following the general procedure for deprotection. The crude product was purified by recrystallization from hexane. Brown solid. Yield 1493 mg (75%). M.p. = 96 °C. $R_f = 0.68$ (silica gel, dichloromethane). 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 20 °C, 500 MHz): 4.31 (s, 3H, $N-CH_3$), 6.73 (d, 1H, $J = 4.5$ Hz, CH), 7.00 (d, 1H, $J = 4.5$ Hz, CH), 7.58–7.61 (m, 1H, CH), 7.81–7.84 (m, 1H, CH), 8.00–8.02 (m, 1H, CH), 8.23–8.24 (m, 1H, CH), 9.73 (s, 1H, CHO) ppm. ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$, APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): $\delta = 32.24, 100.35, 120.52$ – 120.59 (m), 123.09, 125.43, 127.84–127.91 (m), 129.49, 133.95, 150.26, 152.91, 154.38–154.95 (m), 181.14 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $C_{12}H_{11}F_5N_3OS$ ($[M+H]^+$): 340.05375, found 340.05358.

Azo-compound (2a): The title compound was synthesized from 4-aminoacetophenone (168 mg) following the general procedure for diazotization/azo-coupling. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane) and recrystallized from dichloromethane/hexane. Orange solid. Yield 326 mg (77%). M.p. = 135 °C. $R_f = 0.52$ (silica gel, dichloromethane). 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 20 °C, 500 MHz): $\delta = 0.81$ (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.31 (s, 3H, CH_3), 2.62 (s, 3H, CH_3), 3.65 (d, 2H, $J = 11.5$ Hz, CH_2), 3.79 (d, 2H, $J = 11.5$ Hz, CH_2), 4.06 (s, 3H, $N-CH_3$), 5.52 (s, 1H, CH), 6.42 (d, 1H, $J = 4.5$ Hz, CH), 6.69 (d, 1H, $J = 4.5$ Hz, CH), 7.83 (d, 2H, $J = 8.5$ Hz, $2 \times CH$), 8.03 (d, 2H, $J = 9.0$ Hz, $2 \times CH$) ppm. ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$, APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): $\delta = 21.94, 23.28, 26.78, 30.35, 30.93, 77.87, 97.14, 99.49, 110.82, 122.08, 129.35, 135.44, 136.90, 147.80, 156.36, 197.50$ ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $C_{19}H_{23}N_3O_3$ (M^+): 341.17339, found 341.17285.

Azo-compound (2b): The title compound was synthesized from 3-aminoacetophenone (168 mg) following the general procedure for diazotization/azo-coupling. The crude product

was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, hexane/ethyl acetate, 5:2) and recrystallized from dichloromethane/hexane. Ochre solid. Yield 254 mg (60%). M.p. = 106 °C. R_f = 0.35 (silica gel, hexane/ethyl acetate, 5:2). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 500 MHz): δ = 0.81 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.32 (s, 3H, CH_3), 2.65 (s, 3H, CH_3), 3.64 (d, 2H, J = 11.0 Hz, CH_2), 3.79 (d, 2H, J = 11.0 Hz, CH_2), 4.07 (s, 3H, $N\text{-CH}_3$), 5.52 (s, 1H, CH), 6.41 (d, 1H, J = 4.0 Hz, CH), 6.67 (d, 1H, J = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.51–7.54 (m, 1H, CH), 7.93–7.98 (m, 2H, 2 \times CH), 8.33 (s, 1H, CH) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 21.93, 23.28, 26.82, 30.33, 30.95, 77.87, 97.22, 99.03, 110.51, 122.55, 125.87, 128.65, 129.21, 134.75, 137.96, 147.39, 153.66, 197.87 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3$ (M^+): 341.17339, found 341.17277.

Azo-compound (2c): The title compound was synthesized from 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (200 mg) following the general procedure for diazotization/azo-coupling. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane) and recrystallized from hexane. Orange solid. Yield 301 mg (77%). M.p. = 140 °C. R_f = 0.28 (silica gel, dichloromethane). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 500 MHz): δ = 0.81 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.31 (s, 3H, CH_3), 3.64 (d, 2H, J = 11.0 Hz, CH_2), 3.79 (d, 2H, J = 11.5 Hz, CH_2), 4.06 (s, 3H, $N\text{-CH}_3$), 5.52 (s, 1H, CH), 6.42 (d, 1H, J = 4.0 Hz, CH), 6.69 (d, 1H, J = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.68 (d, 2H, J = 8.5 Hz, 2 \times CH), 7.85 (d, 2H, J = 8.0 Hz, 2 \times CH) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 21.93, 23.28, 30.34, 30.92, 77.87, 97.16, 99.50, 110.75, 122.16, 124.11 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 270 Hz), 126.10 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 3.75 Hz), 130.45 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 32.5 Hz), 135.34, 147.53, 155.55 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ (M^+): 367.15021, found 367.14991.

Azo-compound (2d): The title compound was synthesized from 3-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (200 mg) following the general procedure for diazotization/azo-coupling. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane) and recrystallized from hexane. Orange solid. Yield 351 mg (77%). M.p. = 127 °C. R_f = 0.55 (silica gel, DCM). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 500 MHz): δ = 0.81 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.31 (s, 3H, CH_3), 3.64 (d, 2H, J = 11.5 Hz, CH_2), 3.79 (d, 2H, J = 11.0 Hz, CH_2), 4.06 (s, 3H, $N\text{-CH}_3$), 5.52 (s, 1H, CH), 6.41 (d, 1H, J = 4.5 Hz, CH), 6.69 (d, 1H, J = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.53–7.59 (m, 2H, 2 \times CH), 7.94–7.96 (m, 1H, CH), 8.02 (s, 1H, CH) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 21.93, 23.27, 30.34, 30.95, 77.87, 97.17, 99.39, 110.65, 118.67 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 3.75 Hz), 124.00 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 272.5 Hz), 125.40–125.49 (m), 129.46, 131.44 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}}$ = 32.5 Hz), 135.10, 147.35, 153.55 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{F}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ (M^+): 367.15021, found 367.14997.

Azo-compound (2e): The title compound was synthesized from 4-(pentafluorosulfanyl)aniline (272 mg) following the general procedure for diazotization/azo-coupling. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane) and recrystallized from hexane. Ochre solid. Yield 238 mg (45%). M.p. = 159 °C. R_f = 0.65 (silica gel, dichloromethane). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 500 MHz): δ = 0.81 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.31 (s, 3H, CH_3), 3.64 (d, 2H, J = 11.0 Hz, CH_2), 3.79 (d, 2H, J = 11.0 Hz, CH_2), 4.05 (s, 3H, $N\text{-CH}_3$), 5.52 (s, 1H, CH), 6.42 (d, 1H, J = 4.5 Hz, CH), 6.70 (d, 1H, J = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.81 (s, 4H, 4 \times CH) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 21.93, 23.28, 30.35, 30.94, 77.87, 97.11, 99.81, 110.92, 121.86, 126.83–126.90 (m), 135.74, 147.61, 153.32–153.60 (m), 154.81 ppm. HR-FTMALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{20}\text{F}_5\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$ (M^+): 425.11909, found 425.11885.

Azo-compound (2f): The title compound was synthesized from 3-(pentafluorosulfanyl)aniline (272 mg) following the general procedure for diazotization/azo-coupling. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane/hexane, 1:1) and recrystallized from hexane. Orange solid. Yield 402 mg (76%). M.p. = 120 °C. R_f = 0.63 (silica gel, dichloromethane/hexane, 1:1). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 500 MHz): δ = 0.81 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.31 (s, 3H, CH_3), 3.64 (d, 2H, J = 10.5 Hz, CH_2), 3.79 (d, 2H, J = 11.5 Hz, CH_2), 4.05 (s, 3H, $N\text{-CH}_3$), 5.52 (s, 1H, CH), 6.42 (d, 1H, J = 4.5 Hz, CH), 6.69 (d, 1H, J = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.50–7.54 (m, 1H, CH), 7.69–7.71 (m, 1H, CH), 7.90–7.92 (m, 1H, CH), 8.14–8.15 (m, 1H, CH) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 21.94, 23.27, 30.35, 30.97, 77.87, 97.13, 99.68, 110.79, 119.56–119.63 (m), 125.00, 125.88–125.95 (m), 129.12, 135.41, 147.29, 153.54, 154.45–154.73 (m) ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{20}\text{F}_5\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$ (M^+): 425.11909, found 425.11891.

Azo-compound (3a): The title compound was synthesized from **1a** (100 mg) following the general procedure for Knoevenagel condensation. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane) and recrystallized from dichloromethane/hexane. Brownish-red solid. Yield 93 mg (78%). M.p. = 236 °C (decomposition). R_f = 0.18 (silica gel, dichloromethane). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 500 MHz): δ = 2.66 (s, 3H, CH_3), 4.11 (s, 3H, $N\text{-CH}_3$), 6.91 (d, 1H, J = 4.5 Hz, CH), 7.66 (s, 1H, CH), 7.74 (d, 1H, J = 5.0 Hz, CH), 7.94 (d, 2H, J = 8.5 Hz, 2 \times CH), 8.09 (d, 2H, J = 8.5 Hz, 2 \times CH) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 26.88, 30.02, 103.76, 113.93, 114.87, 120.34, 123.13, 129.48, 130.34, 138.87, 141.48, 151.08, 155.48, 197.22 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5\text{O}$ (M^+): 303.11146, found 303.11161.

Azo-compound (3b): The title compound was synthesized from **1b** (100 mg) following the general procedure for Knoevenagel condensation. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, dichloromethane) and recrystallized from dichloromethane/hexane. Red solid. Yield 91 mg (76%). M.p. = 225 °C (decomposition). $R_f = 0.9$ (silica gel, dichloromethane). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 500 MHz): $\delta = 2.68$ (s, 3H, CH_3), 4.11 (s, 3H, $N\text{-CH}_3$), 6.90 (d, 1H, $J = 5.0$ Hz, CH), 7.60–7.64 (m, 1H, CH), 7.66 (s, 1H, CH), 7.74 (d, 1H, $J = 5.0$ Hz, CH), 8.07–8.08 (m, 2H, $2 \times \text{CH}$), 8.43 (s, 1H, CH) ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): $\delta = 26.83, 30.04, 103.58, 114.00, 114.95, 120.35, 122.95, 126.92, 129.66, 130.01, 131.24, 138.28, 141.51, 150.94, 153.24, 197.25$ ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_5\text{O}$ (M^+): 303.11146, found 303.11137.

Azo-compound (3c): The title compound was synthesized from **1c** (110 mg) following the general procedure for Knoevenagel condensation. The crude product was purified by recrystallization from dichloromethane. Red solid. Yield 84 mg (65%). M.p. = 247 °C. $R_f = 0.65$ (silica gel, dichloromethane). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 500 MHz): $\delta = 4.10$ (s, 3H, $N\text{-CH}_3$), 6.91 (d, 1H, $J = 5.0$ Hz, CH), 7.66 (s, 1H, CH), 7.74 (d, 1H, $J = 5.0$ Hz, CH), 7.76 (d, 2H, $J = 8.5$ Hz, $2 \times \text{CH}$), 7.96 (d, 2H, $J = 8.5$ Hz, $2 \times \text{CH}$) ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 125 MHz): $\delta = 30.02, 103.76, 113.88, 114.82, 120.26, 123.16, 123.73$ (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 271.25$ Hz), 126.49 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 3.75$ Hz), 130.32, 132.92 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 32.5$ Hz), 141.51, 150.87, 154.86 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{F}_3\text{N}_5$ (M^+): 329.08828, found 329.08819.

Azo-compound (3d): The title compound was synthesized from **1d** (110 mg) following the general procedure for Knoevenagel condensation. The crude product was purified by recrystallization from dichloromethane/hexane. Red solid. Yield 92 mg (71%). M.p. = 223 °C. $R_f = 0.76$ (silica gel, dichloromethane). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 500 MHz): $\delta = 4.10$ (s, 3H, $N\text{-CH}_3$), 6.90 (d, 1H, $J = 5.0$ Hz, CH), 7.63–7.66 (m, 2H, $2 \times \text{CH}$), 7.74 (d, 2H, $J = 5.0$ Hz, CH), 8.06–8.07 (m, 1H, CH), 8.12 (s, 1H, CH) ppm. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 125 MHz): $\delta = 30.06, 103.70, 113.93, 114.88, 119.21\text{--}119.30$ (m), 120.30, 123.67 (q, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 273.63$ Hz), 126.65, 128.00–128.08 (m), 129.96, 130.18, 131.56–132.35 (m), 141.54, 150.80, 153.02 ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) m/z : calculated for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{F}_3\text{N}_5$ (M^+): 329.08828, found 329.08851.

Azo-compound (3e): The title compound was synthesized from **1e** (133mg) following the general procedure for Knoevenagel condensation. The crude product was purified by recrystallization from dichloromethane/hexane. Red solid. Yield 126 mg (83%). M.p. = 254 °C. $R_f = 0.3$ (silica gel, dichloromethane). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 20 °C, 500 MHz): $\delta = 4.10$ (s, 3H,

N-CH₃), 6.92 (d, 1H, *J* = 5.0 Hz, CH), 7.66 (s, 1H, CH), 7.73 (d, 1H, *J* = 5.0 Hz, CH), 7.88–7.94 (m, 4H, 4 × CH) ppm. ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, APT, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 30.04, 103.90, 113.80, 114.74, 120.22, 122.90, 127.23–127.30 (m), 130.54, 141.50, 150.82, 153.99, 155.23–155.52 (m) ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) *m/z*: calculated for C₁₅H₁₁F₅N₅S ([M+H]⁺): 388.06498, found 388.06520.

Azo-compound (3f): The title compound was synthesized from **1f** (133 mg) following the general procedure for Knoevenagel condensation. The crude product was purified by recrystallization from dichloromethane/hexane. Orange solid. Yield 132 mg (87%). M.p. = 216 °C. *R*_f = 0.27 (silica gel, dichloromethane/hexane, 1:1). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 20 °C, 500 MHz): δ = 4.10 (s, 3H, *N*-CH₃), 6.91 (d, 1H, *J* = 5.5 Hz, CH), 7.61–7.64 (m, 1H, CH), 7.67 (s, 1H, CH), 7.73 (d, 1H, *J* = 5.0 Hz, CH), 7.85–7.86 (m, 1H, CH), 8.02–8.04 (m, 1H, CH), 8.24 (s, 1H, CH) ppm. ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 20 °C, 125 MHz): δ = 30.09, 103.88, 113.85, 114.79, 120.07–120.14 (m), 120.27, 126.26, 128.41–128.48 (m), 129.67, 130.38, 141.53, 150.66, 152.85, 154.62–154.91 (m) ppm. HR-FT-MALDI-MS (DCTB) *m/z*: calculated for C₁₅H₁₁F₅N₅S ([M+H]⁺): 388.06498, found 388.06488.

2. X-ray Analysis

Full-set of diffraction data for **1b** and **2f** was collected at 150(2)K with a Bruker D8-Venture diffractometer equipped with Mo (Mo/K_α radiation; λ = 0.71073 Å) microfocus X-ray (I_μS) sources, Photon CMOS detector and Oxford Cryosystems cooling device was used for data collection.

The frames were integrated with the Bruker SAINT software package using a narrow-frame algorithm. Data were corrected for absorption effects using the Multi-Scan method (SADABS). Obtained data were treated by XT-version 2014/5 and SHELXL-2014/7 software implemented in APEX4 v2021.10-0 (Bruker AXS) system.^[65]

Hydrogen atoms were mostly localized on a difference Fourier map, however, to ensure uniformity of treatment of crystal, all hydrogen were recalculated into idealized positions (riding model) and assigned temperature factors H_{iso}(H) = 1.2 U_{eq} (pivot atom) or of 1.5U_{eq} (methyl). Hydrogen atoms in methyl, methylene, methine moieties and hydrogen atoms in aromatic rings were placed with C-H distances of 0.96, 0.97, 0.98 and 0.93 Å.

$R_{\text{int}} = \sum |F_o^2 - F_{o,\text{mean}}^2| / \sum F_o^2$, $S = [\sum (w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2) / (N_{\text{diffrs}} - N_{\text{params}})]^{1/2}$ for all data, $R(F) = \sum ||F_o| - |F_c|| / \sum |F_o|$ for observed data, $wR(F^2) = [\sum (w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2) / (\sum w(F_o^2)^2)]^{1/2}$ for all data.

Crystallographic data for structural analyses have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC no. 2368880 and 2368881 for **1b** and **2f**. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EY, UK (fax: +44-1223-336033; e-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www: <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

Figure S 1. Crystal packing of **1b**.

Figure S 2. Crystal packing of **2f**.

3. Thermal Analysis

Table S 1. Thermal properties of target compounds **1a–f**, **2a–f** and **3a–f**.

Compound	T_i^a [°C]	T_5^a [°C]	T_m^b [°C]	T_d^b [°C]
1a	178	206	163	230
1b	150	191	147	240
1c	122	152	122	265
1d	119	150	136	255
1e	128	162	129	250
1f	136	162	96	250
2a	203	230	135	230
2b	196	228	106	250
2c	154	184	140	270
2d	160	192	127	280
2e	168	201	159	245
2f	172	205	120	255
3a	236	249	- ^c	245 ^c
3b	225	238	- ^c	235 ^c
3c	208	239	247	275
3d	192	224	223	270
3e	220	245	254	260
3f	208	237	216	275

^a Determined by TGA in open alumina crucibles under an N₂ inert atmosphere and with a heating rate of 3 °C min⁻¹ within the range of 25–400 °C. The initial temperature of thermal degradation was determined as the last common point of the TGA curve and its first derivation (DTG curve). The temperature of 5% weight loss was determined by a gradual horizontal step on the TGA curve. ^b Determined by DSC in aluminous crucibles closed with holed lid under an N₂ inert atmosphere and with a scan rate of 5 °C min⁻¹ within the range of 25–400 °C. The melting points and liquid phase decomposition temperatures were determined as the point of intersection of the baseline and tangent of the peak (onset point). ^c Thermal decomposition of solid phase prior to melting.

Figure S 3. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **1a**.

Figure S 4. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **1b**.

Figure S 5. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **1c**.

Figure S 6. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **1d**.

Figure S 7. TGA curve of compound **1d** containing an isothermal step showing sublimation.

Figure S 8. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **1e**.

Figure S 9. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **1f**.

Figure S 10. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **2a**.

Figure S 11. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **2b**.

Figure S 12. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **2c**.

Figure S 13. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **2d**.

Figure S 14. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **2e**.

Figure S 15. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **2f**.

Figure S 16. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **3a**.

Figure S 17. TGA curve of compound **3a** containing an isothermal step showing thermal decomposition.

Figure S 18. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **3b**.

Figure S 19. TGA curve of compound **3b** containing an isothermal step showing thermal decomposition.

Figure S 20. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **3c**.

Figure S 21. TGA curve of compound **3c** containing an isothermal step showing sublimation.

Figure S 22. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **3d**.

Figure S 23. TGA curve of compound **3d** containing an isothermal step showing sublimation.

Figure S 24. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **3e**.

Figure S 25. TGA curve of compound **3e** containing an isothermal step showing sublimation.

Figure S 26. TGA curve (black) and DSC curve (red) of compound **3f**.

Figure S 27. TGA curve of compound **3f** containing an isothermal step showing sublimation.

4. Electrochemistry

Figure S 28. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **1a** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 29. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **1b** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 30. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **1c** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 31. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **1d** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 32. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **1e** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 33. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **1f** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 34. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **2a** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 35. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **2b** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 36. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **2c** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 37. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **2d** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 38. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **2e** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 39. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **2f** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 40. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **3a** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 41. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **3b** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 42. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **3c** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 43. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **3d** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 44. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **3e** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

Figure S 45. Cyclic voltammogram of chromophore **3f** measured in acetonitrile containing 0.1 M Bu₄NPF₆ at glassy carbon electrode.

5. Linear optical properties

Due to a partial undesirable $E \rightarrow Z$ switching induced by a xenon lamp of the spectrophotometer during measurement of thermally relaxed samples, dark-adapted spectra had to be measured using chosen points of wavelength and subsequently optimized in the meaning of Gaussian model given in the Equation S1:

$$A = P_1 \exp\left(-\frac{(\nu - P_2)^2}{P_3^2}\right), \quad (\text{S1})$$

where A is absorbance and ν is wavenumber in kiloKaysers unit. The parameters P_1 – P_3 were determined from experimentally obtained data by non-linear regression based on genetic algorithm using OPstat software.^[66]

The mathematical model used for deconvolution is given in the Equation S2. Variables A and ν are absorbance and wavenumber, respectively, A_{\max} and ν_{\max} are absorbance and wavenumber in absorption maximum of the specific band and $\Delta\nu$ is half-width of the band.

$$A = A_{\max} \exp\left[-(4\ln 2) \frac{(\nu - \nu_{\max})^2}{\Delta\nu^2}\right] \quad (\text{S2})$$

Figure S 46. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **1a** corresponding to 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 47. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **1b** corresponding to 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 48. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **1c** corresponding to 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 49. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **1d** corresponding to 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 50. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **1e** corresponding to 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 51. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **1f** corresponding to 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 52. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **2a** corresponding to 415 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 53. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **2b** corresponding to 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 54. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **2c** corresponding to 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 55. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **2d** corresponding to 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 56. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **2e** corresponding to 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 57. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **2f** corresponding to 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve.

Figure S 58. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **3a** corresponding to 450 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve. The particular π - π^* bands for (*Z*)-isomer (red) and (*E*)-isomer (green) were deconvoluted within the 450 nm adapted spectra.

Figure S 59. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **3b** corresponding to 450 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve. The particular π - π^* bands for (*Z*)-isomer (red) and (*E*)-isomer (green) were deconvoluted within the 450 nm adapted spectra.

Figure S 60. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **3c** corresponding to 465 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve. The particular π - π^* bands for (*Z*)-isomer (red) and (*E*)-isomer (green) were deconvoluted within the 465 nm adapted spectra.

Figure S 61. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **3d** corresponding to 465 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve. The particular π - π^* bands for (*Z*)-isomer (red) and (*E*)-isomer (green) were deconvoluted within the 465 nm adapted spectra.

Figure S 62. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **3e** corresponding to 465 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve. The particular π - π^* bands for (*Z*)-isomer (red) and (*E*)-isomer (green) were deconvoluted within the 465 nm adapted spectra.

Figure S 63. UV-Vis absorption spectra of compound **3f** corresponding to 470 nm adapted PSS (violet) and dark-adapted PSS (black) in DCE at a concentration of 5×10^{-5} M. The experimentally obtained points (blue) were fitted with black curve. The particular π - π^* bands for (*Z*)-isomer (red) and (*E*)-isomer (green) were deconvoluted within the 470 nm adapted spectra.

6. Thermal Kinetics

Figure S 64. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1a** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 65. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1b** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 66. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1c** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 67. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1d** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 68. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1e** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 69. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1f** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 70. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **2a** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 71. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **2b** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 72. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **2c** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 73. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **2d** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 74. Thermal kinetics curve of compound 2e obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 75. Thermal kinetics curve of compound 2f obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 76. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **3a** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 77. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **3b** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 78. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **3c** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 79. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **3d** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 80. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **3e** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 81. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **3f** obtained by UV-Vis monitoring (DCE, 20 °C).

Figure S 82. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1a** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 83. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1b** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 84. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1c** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 85. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1d** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 86. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1e** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 87. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **1f** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 88. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **2a** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure S 89. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **2b** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure S 90. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **2c** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure S 91. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **2d** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure S 92. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **2e** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 93. Thermal kinetics curve of compound **2f** obtained by ^1H NMR monitoring (CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

7. ^1H NMR Spectra of Photostationary States

Figure S 94. ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 $^\circ\text{C}$) of azo-photoswitch **1a** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

Figure S 95. ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 $^\circ\text{C}$) of azo-photoswitch **1b** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

Figure S 96. ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 $^\circ\text{C}$) of azo-photoswitch **1c** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

Figure S 97. ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 $^\circ\text{C}$) of azo-photoswitch **1d** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

Figure S 98. ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 $^\circ\text{C}$) of azo-photoswitch **1e** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

Figure S 99. ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 $^\circ\text{C}$) of azo-photoswitch **1f** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

Figure S 100. ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 $^\circ\text{C}$) of azo-photoswitch **2a** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 415 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

Figure S 101. ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 $^\circ\text{C}$) of azo-photoswitch **2b** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

Figure S 102. ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20°C) of azo-photoswitch **2c** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

Figure S 103. ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20°C) of azo-photoswitch **2d** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

Figure S 104. ¹H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C) of azo-photoswitch **2e** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

Figure S 105. ¹H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C) of azo-photoswitch **2f** corresponding to the dark-adapted PSS (black), 400 nm adapted PSS (violet) and 525 nm adapted PSS (green).

8. Fatigue Resistance

Figure S 106. Fatigue resistance of compound **1a** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 107. Fatigue resistance of compound **1b** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 108. Fatigue resistance of compound **1c** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 109. Fatigue resistance of compound **1d** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 110. Fatigue resistance of compound **1e** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 111. Fatigue resistance of compound **1f** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 112. Fatigue resistance of compound **2a** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 113. Fatigue resistance of compound **2b** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 114. Fatigue resistance of compound **2c** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 115. Fatigue resistance of compound **2d** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 116. Fatigue resistance of compound **2e** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 117. Fatigue resistance of compound **2f** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 118. Fatigue resistance of compound **3a** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 119. Fatigue resistance of compound **3b** verified by switching with 400 nm and 450 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 120. Fatigue resistance of compound **3c** verified by switching with 400 nm and 465 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 121. Fatigue resistance of compound **3d** verified by switching with 400 nm and 465 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 122. Fatigue resistance of compound 3e verified by switching with 400 nm and 465 nm within ten cycles.

Figure S 123. Fatigue resistance of compound 3f verified by switching with 400 nm and 470 nm within ten cycles.

9. ¹H and ¹³C NMR Spectra

Figure S 124. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **1a** (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

Figure S 125. ¹³C NMR APT spectrum of compound **1a** (125 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

Figure S 126. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **1b** (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

Figure S 127. ^{13}C NMR APT spectrum of compound **1b** (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 128. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **1c** (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 129. ^{13}C NMR APT spectrum of compound **1c** (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 133. ¹³C NMR APT spectrum of compound **1e** (125 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

Figure S 134. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **1f** (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

Figure S 135. ¹³C NMR APT spectrum of compound **1f** (125 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

Figure S 137. ^{13}C NMR APT spectrum of compound **2a** (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 138. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **2b** (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 139. ^{13}C NMR APT spectrum of compound **2b** (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 140. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **2c** (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 141. ^{13}C NMR APT spectrum of compound **2c** (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 142. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2d** (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

Figure S 143. ¹³C NMR APT spectrum of compound **2d** (125 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

Figure S 144. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2e** (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

Figure S 148. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **3a** (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 149. ^{13}C NMR APT spectrum of compound **3a** (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 150. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **3b** (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 °C).

Figure S 151. ^{13}C NMR APT spectrum of compound **3b** (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 $^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure S 152. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **3c** (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 $^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure S 153. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **3c** (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , 20 $^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure S 157. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **3e** (125 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

Figure S 158. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **3f** (500 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

Figure S 159. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **3f** (125 MHz, CDCl₃, 20 °C).

10. Mass Spectra

Figure S 160. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **1a**.

Figure S 161. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **1b**.

Figure S 162. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **1c**.

Figure S 163. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **1d**.

Figure S 164. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **1e**.

Figure S 165. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **1f**.

Figure S 166. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **2a**.

Figure S 167. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **2b**.

Figure S 168. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **2c**.

Figure S 169. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **2d**.

Figure S 170. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **2e**.

Figure S 171. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **2f**.

Figure S 172. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **3a**.

Figure S 173. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **3b**.

Figure S 174. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **3c**.

Figure S 175. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **3d**.

Figure S 176. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **3e**.

Figure S 177. Experimental (up) and calculated (down) HR-FT-MALDI-MS spectrum of **3f**.

11. HRS Experiments

Definition of the HRS properties

Assuming a polarized incident laser light and observation of a vertically polarized scattered light at 90° (perpendicular to the horizontal plane of polarization), the total HRS hyperpolarizability reads:

$$\beta_{HRS} = \sqrt{\langle \beta_{ZZZ}^2 \rangle + \langle \beta_{ZXX}^2 \rangle} \quad (S3)$$

where $\langle \beta_{ZZZ}^2 \rangle$ and $\langle \beta_{ZXX}^2 \rangle$ are macroscopic isotropic averages proportional to the scattered light intensities for vertically and horizontally plane-polarized incident beams, respectively oriented parallel to the Z and X axes of the laboratory frame. The full expressions of $\langle \beta_{ZZZ}^2 \rangle$ and $\langle \beta_{ZXX}^2 \rangle$ in terms of molecular β -tensor components are given in Eqs. S11 and S12. Their quotient

$$DR = \langle \beta_{ZZZ}^2 \rangle / \langle \beta_{ZXX}^2 \rangle \quad (S4)$$

is referred to as the depolarization ratio, and provides information on the dipolar/octupolar symmetry of the second-order NLO response. A limiting DR value of 3/2 or 9 stands for pure octupolar or dipolar responses, respectively. In contrast, a prototype push-pull π -conjugated molecule, for which the β tensor is largely dominated by the diagonal component parallel to the molecular charge transfer axis, displays a DR value close to 5.

β_{HRS} is also analyzed in terms of its irreducible spherical representations; in the static case, it reads:

$$\beta_{HRS} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{9}\beta_1^2 + \frac{2}{21}\beta_3^2} \quad (S5)$$

where β_1 and β_3 are the dipolar and octupolar contributions, respectively. Their ratio is referred to as the nonlinear anisotropy parameter and can be related to the depolarization ratio:

$$\rho = \frac{\beta_3}{\beta_1} = \sqrt{\frac{7}{6}} \sqrt{\frac{9-DR}{2DR-3}} \quad (S6)$$

Acquisition of the HRS properties

An OPG picosecond laser source (signal: 720-1000 nm, idler: 1150-2200 nm) is used as probing source to adjust the incident energy (ω) to tune the HRS (2ω). A block power, constituted of a half-wave plate and a polarizer, is placed after the source in order to control the incident intensity and deliver linear vertical polarization. This fundamental relative intensity is precisely determined via the measurement of the scattered light intensity by a mirror routed through an

optical fiber to a photodiode connected to an oscilloscope. Then, the incident polarization state is controlled using a motorized half-wave plate (with rotation angle $\Psi/2$). Vertically (V) polarized incident beams correspond to $\Psi = 90^\circ$, horizontally (H) polarized incident beams correspond to $\Psi = 0^\circ$. This tunability of the incident linear beam polarization allows to probe different beta tensor components. The scattered light is collected at 90° selecting the vertical polarization using an analyzer. A modified Raman spectrograph allows the collection of the HRS signal at 2ω using a grating (830 grooves/mm) optimized in the visible range [500-950 nm] and a 1024x256 pixels CCD detector cooled by a Peltier unit down to -70° Celsius. The β_{HRS} of each compound was investigated in chloroform solution using the solvent as internal reference.^[67] An incident excitation wavelength of 1300 nm has been chosen as a good compromise to avoid both absorption of the fundamental beam from chloroform in the near IR range (ω) and absorption of the scattered harmonic beam (2ω) from the azo-samples.

For a diluted binary solution composed of a solvent (S, here chloroform) and a solute (X, here the azo-derivative), the total incoherent scattered second-harmonic (HRS) light is given by^[67]

$$I_{2\omega}^{\Psi V} = G\{C_S[|\beta_S|^2 C_{\Psi V}]_S + C_X[|\beta_X|^2 C_{\Psi V}]_X\} I_\omega^2 10^{-\varepsilon_{2\omega} \delta C_X} \quad (S7a)$$

with the orientational average for the solvent and the solute defined (using only linear incident polarization in this configuration) as

$$[C_{\Psi V}]_i = \cos^4 \Psi + (1 + DR_i) \sin^2 \Psi \cos^2 \Psi + DR_i \sin^4 \Psi \quad (i = S, X) \quad (S7b)$$

The last term in eq S7a accounts for absorption losses at the second harmonic wavelength, with $\varepsilon_{2\omega}$ the molar extinction coefficient at frequency 2ω and δ the optical path length of the scattered light. Note that the one-photon absorption of the azo-derivatives at the harmonic frequency was either zero or sufficiently weak to avoid spurious measurements. In addition, in a diluted regime, the solvent contribution (first global term in eq S7a) is assumed to be a constant and serves as an internal reference since chloroform has a non-zero HRS response.

Power Scans: Scaling the Quadratic Dependence of the HRS Signal

The HRS amplitude can be obtained by performing first power scans, *i.e.*, by determining the coefficient of the quadratic dependence of the scattered intensity analyzed vertically ($I_{2\omega}^{VV}$) as a function of the incident intensity (I_ω) and for different solute concentrations (C_X) (eq S7a). The polarization configuration was set to vertical-vertical (VV), *i.e.*, with vertically polarized incident light and scattered light analyzed vertically. Power scans were performed on diluted solutions at different concentrations (varying between 10^{-2} to 10^{-3} M, depending of the NLO

response of each compound). All experiments were carried out at room temperature. Each data point of the power scan was an average of three accumulations with an acquisition time of 20s to achieve a good signal-to-noise ratio, depending of the solution. Coefficient of quadratic dependence were obtained by fitting the power curves as function of incident power (I_ω) and solute concentration (C_X) using a custom-built 2D fitting function of the form:

$$I_{2\omega}^{VV}(I_\omega, C_X) = (|p_1| + |p_2|C_X)(I_\omega - p_3)^2 \quad (S7c)$$

where p_i ($i=1-3$) are fitting parameters. The extracted quantity is $C_{vv}\beta^2 = R \cdot p_2/p_1$, with the constant (internal) reference value for chloroform at 1300 nm equal to $R = C_S[|\beta_S|^2 C_{\Psi V}]_S = 6092$ atomic unit (a. u.), using the T convention.^[58]

Polarization Scans: Quantifying the Dipolar/Octupolar Character of the HRS Response (DR)

The depolarization ratio (DR) was obtained by performing a polarization scan, *i.e.*, through stepwise variation of the incident light linear plane of polarization, at constant incident power. It is thus necessary to measure the scattered intensity, from a binary solution with a chosen concentration and from the pure solvent, to extract the contribution of the azo compound (Eq. S7b). The polarization configuration was set to Ψ -V (where Ψ is the variable angle of the half-wave plate) for the incident and scattered lights, respectively. Polarization scans were performed between 0° and $+180^\circ$ in 5° steps on the most concentrated binary solution. All experiments were carried out at room temperature. Each data point of the polarization scan was an average of three accumulations with an acquisition time of 20s (1300 nm) each. The DR value was determined by fitting the polarization curve using a constrained custom-built fitting function of the form:

$$I_{2\omega}^{\Psi V} = A[\cos^4(\Psi - \Psi_0) + (1 + DR) \sin^2(\Psi - \Psi_0) \cos^2(\Psi - \Psi_0) + DR \sin^4(\Psi - \Psi_0)] \quad (S7d)$$

where A (intensity factor), Ψ_0 (angular offset) and DR (depolarization ratio) are fitting parameters.

All other quantities are calculated from the three fitted terms (p_1 , p_2 and DR) obtained through the power scans and the polarization scan for each compound. The anisotropy parameter ρ is obtained from Eq. S7d. The dipolar hyperpolarizability $\beta_1 = (R \cdot p_1/p_2)/(1/5 + 2\rho^2/35)$ is obtained from equations S7c and S7d. Next, the octupolar hyperpolarizability β_3 and the HRS amplitude β_{HRS} are calculated using equations S6 and S4, respectively.

HRS data for compound 3a

Origin	Slope	$C_{vv} \cdot \beta^2$	DR	ρ	C_{vv}	β_1 (at. unit)	β_3 (at. unit)	β_{HRS} (at. unit)
4,26E+02	1,02E+05	1,46E+06	3,55	1,25	0,289	2,25E+03	2,81E+03	1,37E+03

HRS data for compound 3b

Origin	Slope	$C_{vv} \cdot \beta^2$	DR	ρ	C_{vv}	β_1 (at. unit)	β_3 (at. unit)	β_{HRS} (at. unit)
4,74E+02	1,51E+05	1,94E+06	4,47	0,94	0,251	2,78E+03	2,63E+03	1,54E+03

HRS data for compound 3c

Origin	Slope	$C_{vv} \cdot \beta^2$	DR	ρ	C_{vv}	β_1 (at. unit)	β_3 (at. unit)	β_{HRS} (at. unit)
4,21E+02	1,52E+05	2,20E+06	4,34	0,98	0,255	2,94E+03	2,88E+03	1,65E+03

HRS data for compound 3d

Origin	Slope	$C_{vv} \cdot \beta^2$	DR	ρ	C_{vv}	β_1 (at. unit)	β_3 (at. unit)	β_{HRS} (at. unit)
4,91E+02	1,17E+05	1,46E+06	4,74	0,88	0,244	2,45E+03	2,14E+03	1,33E+03

HRS data for compound 3e

Origin	Slope	$C_{vv} \cdot \beta^2$	DR	ρ	C_{vv}	β_1 (at. unit)	β_3 (at. unit)	β_{HRS} (at. unit)
4,91E+02	6,93E+04	8,59E+05	3,69	1,19	0,281	1,75E+03	2,08E+03	1,05E+03

HRS data for compound 3f

Origin	Slope	$C_{vv} \cdot \beta^2$	DR	ρ	C_{vv}	β_1 (at. unit)	β_3 (at. unit)	β_{HRS} (at. unit)
4,26E+02	5,46E+04	7,81E+05	3,99	1,08	0,267	1,71E+03	1,85E+03	9,88E+02

12. DFT Calculations

Table S 2. Boltzmann probability p_B^X , Relative Gibbs energy ΔG^X , magnitude of the total dipole moment μ^X , and bond length alternation BLA^X for the various conformers of the three series of azo-compounds, as computed at the ω B97X-D/6-311G(d) level in dichloromethane. Only conformers with $\Delta G^X < 2$ kcal.mol⁻¹ have been retained.

Compound	p_B^E	ΔG^E [kcal.mol ⁻¹]	μ^E [Debye]	BLA^E [Å]	p_B^Z	ΔG^Z [kcal.mol ⁻¹]	μ^Z [Debye]	BLA^Z [Å]
1a	0.3897	0.2422	4.61	0.151	0.9301	-	3.75	0.168
	0.0238	1.8982	2.53	0.150	0.0699	1.5330	3.88	0.166
	0.5865	-	1.43	0.152				
1b	0.2207	0.3545	4.23	0.153	0.5909	-	6.79	0.172
	0.4016	-	1.77	0.153	0.0564	1.3912	1.42	0.171
	0.1488	0.5880	6.25	0.154	0.2284	0.5629	6.79	0.172
	0.0186	1.8198	6.69	0.152	0.0558	1.3981	1.42	0.171
	0.1940	0.4311	2.65	0.153	0.0351	1.6717	6.31	0.171
	0.0163	1.8969	2.01	0.152	0.0334	1.7024	0.98	0.171
1c	1.0000	-	2.20	0.152	0.3943	0.2541	1.23	0.168
					0.6057	-	1.23	0.168
1d	0.4140	0.1217	1.23	0.153	0.2914	0.1770	3.98	0.170
	0.0246	1.7934	5.80	0.151	0.0260	1.6077	3.12	0.168
	0.5085	-	4.31	0.153	0.2635	0.2366	4.03	0.170
	0.0529	1.3403	3.16	0.151	0.0263	1.6014	3.12	0.168
1e					0.3928	-	3.51	0.170
	0.9645	-	4.45	0.151	0.3876	0.0264	2.47	0.166
	0.0355	1.9553	2.74	0.149	0.0671	1.0649	6.07	0.163
					0.4052	-	2.36	0.166
1f					0.1400	0.6294	6.09	0.163
	0.1143	1.2130	3.46	0.152	0.4317	0.0182	5.26	0.169
	0.8857	-	6.35	0.152	0.0616	1.1709	5.18	0.166
					0.4451	-	5.26	0.169
2a					0.0616	1.1715	5.18	0.166
	0.0583	1.0097	9.82	0.140	0.2469	0.2761	8.36	0.154
	0.3208	-	5.91	0.140	0.3596	0.0533	8.03	0.156
	0.1224	0.5704	9.81	0.140	0.3935	-	8.03	0.156
	0.2907	0.0584	5.91	0.140				
	0.1004	0.6877	9.28	0.142				
2b	0.1074	0.6482	6.14	0.142				
	0.1955	-	7.72	0.144	0.1368	0.4945	8.18	0.157
	0.0873	0.4775	2.08	0.144	0.2148	0.2272	6.33	0.157
	0.0621	0.6796	8.48	0.144	0.1213	0.5654	8.32	0.157
	0.0956	0.4236	8.69	0.144	0.3152	-	7.63	0.157
	0.1643	0.1029	7.70	0.144	0.1529	0.4286	7.92	0.159
	0.0820	0.5146	2.08	0.144	0.0591	0.9915	7.19	0.159
	0.0621	0.6790	8.48	0.144				
	0.0943	0.4317	8.69	0.144				
	0.0482	0.8289	7.70	0.146				
	0.0419	0.9124	8.27	0.146				
	0.0667	0.6369	7.61	0.146				
2c	0.6610	-	8.11	0.141	0.2730	0.2140	8.41	0.154
	0.0763	1.2789	8.30	0.139	0.3918	-	8.38	0.154
	0.2627	0.5466	8.00	0.143	0.3353	0.0922	7.82	0.156
2d	0.2692	-	9.15	0.142	0.4919	-	7.66	0.155
	0.1365	0.4022	5.10	0.142	0.1408	0.7411	7.60	0.158
	0.2518	0.0395	9.17	0.142	0.1206	0.8327	8.16	0.156
	0.1372	0.3991	5.10	0.142	0.2468	0.4085	7.66	0.155
	0.0565	0.9243	8.50	0.145				
	0.1489	0.3508	5.30	0.144				
2e	0.1770	0.3734	10.72	0.137	0.5144	-	10.25	0.151
	0.1779	0.3702	10.72	0.137	0.4105	0.1337	10.21	0.152
	0.3324	-	10.76	0.139	0.0752	1.1389	9.62	0.154
	0.3126	0.0364	10.76	0.139				
2f	0.0899	1.2832	11.81	0.140	0.0708	1.0856	9.06	0.153
	0.0537	1.5888	6.15	0.140	0.1231	0.7580	8.23	0.154

	0.0348	1.8455	11.82	0.140	0.1235	0.7561	8.23	0.154
	0.0369	1.8103	6.11	0.140	0.0703	1.0893	9.06	0.153
	0.7847	-	6.75	0.142	0.1698	0.5673	8.37	0.156
					0.4425	-	8.44	0.156
3a	0.5270	-	8.93	0.152	0.5003	-	6.85	0.172
	0.4730	0.0640	8.15	0.152	0.4997	0.0001	6.85	0.172
3b	0.3206	-	7.09	0.153	0.1741	0.6815	7.62	0.175
	0.2107	0.2485	12.96	0.153	0.1382	0.8183	8.79	0.175
	0.2550	0.1355	12.33	0.154	0.1376	0.8208	8.79	0.175
	0.2137	0.2403	6.90	0.153	0.5500	-	7.58	0.175
3c	1.0000	-	6.89	0.153	1.0000	-	7.00	0.173
3d	0.4659	0.0809	9.50	0.153	0.7625	-	7.75	0.173
	0.5341	-	8.73	0.153	0.2375	0.6909	6.45	0.174
3e	1.0000	-	4.08	0.153	1.0000	-	7.95	0.171
3f	0.1742	0.9218	9.22	0.153	0.7031	-	7.39	0.173
	0.8258	-	7.78	0.152	0.2969	0.5108	8.88	0.173

Figure S 178. Different E conformers of compound **1b**, with the relative Gibbs free energies (in kcal mol⁻¹). Blue arrows represent the orientation of the dipole moment.

Figure S 179. Different E conformers of compound **2f**, with the relative Gibbs free energies (in kcal mol⁻¹). Blue arrows represent the orientation of the dipole moment.

Figure S 180. Evolution of the bond length alternation (BLA, Å) within compounds **1-3** in their *E* and *Z* isomers. Horizontal lines represent the averaged BLA along a *E/Z* series.

Figure S 181. Electrostatic potential map of the different (*E*)- and (*Z*)-conformers of **3a**. Positive values of electrostatic potential (in blue) correspond to low electron density regions, while negative values (in red) correspond to high electron density regions.

Figure S 182. Shape of the frontier MOs (from left to right: HOMO-1, HOMO and LUMO) of (*E*)-isomers of formyl derivatives **1a-1f**, computed at the M06/6-311+G(d) level in dichloromethane.

Figure S 183. Shape of the frontier MOs (from left to right: HOMO-1, HOMO and LUMO) of (*E*)-isomers of acetal derivatives **2a-2f**, computed at the M06/6-311+G(d) level in dichloromethane.

Figure S 184. Shape of the frontier MOs (from left to right: HOMO-1, HOMO and LUMO) of (*E*)-isomers of dicyanovinyl derivatives **3a-3f**, computed at the M06/6-311+G(d) level in dichloromethane.

Figure S 185. Correlation between experimental and calculated HOMO-LUMO gaps for (*E*)-isomers in the three series of compounds.

Table S 3. Transition wavelengths (λ^X), energies (in parenthesis), and associated oscillator strengths (f^X) related to the main absorption bands in the three series of azo-compounds, as computed at the M06/6-311+G(d) level in dichloromethane.

Compound	$\lambda_{TDDFT(EDC)}^E$ [nm (eV)]	$f_{TDDFT(EDC)}^E$	Electronic transition	$\lambda_{TDDFT(EDC)}^Z$ [nm (eV)]	$f_{TDDFT(EDC)}^Z$	Electronic transition
1a	417 (2.98)	1.1619	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	342 (3.62)	0.1887	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
				336 (3.69)	0.3529	$S_0 \rightarrow S_3$
1b	401 (3.09)	1.0084	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	343 (3.62) 335 (3.71)	0.2396 0.1602	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$
1c	403 (3.08)	1.0452	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	331 (3.75)	0.4602	$S_0 \rightarrow S_3$
1d	400 (3.10)	1.0020	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	342 (3.63)	0.1028	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
				332 (3.74)	0.3657	$S_0 \rightarrow S_3$
1e	406 (3.06)	1.0694	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	329 (3.77)	0.6508	$S_0 \rightarrow S_3$
1f	401 (3.09)	0.9927	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	345 (3.59)	0.1071	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
				336 (3.69)	0.2223	$S_0 \rightarrow S_3$
				333 (3.72)	0.1520	$S_0 \rightarrow S_4$
2a	416 (2.98)	1.1748	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	324 (3.83)	0.5861	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
				295 (4.20)	0.1114	$S_0 \rightarrow S_4$
2b	398 (3.12)	0.9633	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	317 (3.91)	0.1875	$S_0 \rightarrow S_3$
				312 (3.98)	0.3434	$S_0 \rightarrow S_4$
2c	397 (3.12)	1.0497	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	315 (3.94)	0.6040	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
2d	397 (3.13)	0.9893	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	313 (3.96)	0.6036	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
2e	403 (3.08)	1.0754	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	318 (3.90)	0.6270	$S_0 \rightarrow S_3$
2f	397 (3.13)	0.9754	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	323 (3.84)	0.4392	$S_0 \rightarrow S_3$
				306 (4.05)	0.1307	$S_0 \rightarrow S_4$
3a	464 (2.68)	1.641	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	527 (2.36)	0.163	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$
				390 (3.18)	0.884	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
3b	450 (2.75)	1.524	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	531 (2.34)	0.198	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$
				389 (3.18)	0.789	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
3c	451 (2.75)	1.535	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	520 (2.38)	0.142	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$
				387 (3.20)	0.914	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
3d	450 (2.76)	1.502	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	525 (2.36)	0.180	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$
				387 (3.21)	0.851	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
3e	454 (2.73)	1.546	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	513 (2.42)	0.138	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$
				387 (3.20)	0.936	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$
3f	450 (2.76)	1.491	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$	516 (2.40)	0.154	$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$
				386 (3.21)	0.911	$S_0 \rightarrow S_2$

Figure S 186. Absorption spectra computed at the TDDFT/M06/6-311+G(d) in chloroform for compounds **1-3** in their (*E*)- (left) and (*Z*)-isomers (right), with theoretical absorption peaks enlarged using Gaussian functions with full width at half-maximum of 0.3 eV.

Figure S 187. Correlation between experimental and calculated $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition energies for (*E*)-isomers in the three series of compounds.

Table S 4. Static and dynamic nonlinear optical properties of azo-compounds **1–3** in their (*E*)-isomers, as calculated at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level in chloroform.

Compound	β_{HRS}^{static} [a.u.]	β_{HRS}^{1300nm} [a.u.]	DR^{static}	DR^{1300nm}
1a	2316	3303	3.85	4.30
1b	764	1106	3.34	4.12
1c	1308	1851	3.24	3.86
1d	1076	1488	3.15	3.79
1e	1991	2819	3.72	4.20
1f	1450	1989	3.77	4.25
2a	5001	7019	4.63	4.80
2b	2545	3408	4.98	5.09
2c	3113	4193	4.47	4.69
2d	2725	3623	4.57	4.77
2e	3757	5156	4.45	4.68
2f	2954	3875	4.59	4.78
3a	2475	3836	2.69	3.41
3b	1828	2137	2.91	2.94
3c	1771	2379	2.32	2.75
3d	1605	1935	2.36	2.51
3e	2434	3874	2.84	3.61
3f	1795	2545	2.48	3.08

Table S 5. Static and dynamic nonlinear optical properties of azo-compounds **1–3** in their (*Z*)-isomers, as calculated at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level in chloroform.

Compound	β_{HRS}^{static} [a.u.]	β_{HRS}^{1300nm} [a.u.]	DR^{static}	DR^{1300nm}
1a	622	628	2.78	2.87
1b	425	439	1.83	1.88
1c	403	377	2.01	2.02
1d	409	404	1.97	2.03
1e	414	390	2.49	2.73
1f	410	390	2.23	2.18
2a	1072	1200	5.53	5.87
2b	868	934	5.08	5.44
2c	823	889	4.73	5.03
2d	834	889	4.70	4.96
2e	883	964	4.91	5.21
2f	847	911	5.01	5.22
3a	1474	2155	2.73	3.49
3b	1785	2706	3.95	4.48
3c	1470	2089	3.41	4.11
3d	1620	2391	3.64	4.28
3e	1255	1686	3.06	3.78
3f	1347	1902	3.28	4.00

Evaluation of the HRS hyperpolarizability using the two-state approximation

The two-state approximation (TSA) assumes that the lowest-energy dipole-allowed transition (here $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$) is the only one contributing to the sum-over-state expansion of the HRS hyperpolarizability:

$$\beta_{HRS,TSA}^{1300nm} = \beta_{HRS,TSA}^{static} |F(\omega)| \quad (S8)$$

with

$$\beta_{HRS,TSA}^{static} = 9 \sqrt{\frac{6}{35}} \frac{f_{02} \Delta\mu_{02}}{\Delta E_{02}^3} \quad (S9)$$

In equation S8, ΔE_{02} and f_{02} are the energy and oscillator strength associated to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition, and $\Delta\mu_{02}$ the variation of the permanent dipole moment. $F(\omega)$ is the frequency dispersion factor that depends on the photon energy $\hbar\omega$ of the incident light beam:

$$|F(\omega)| = \frac{\Delta E_{02}^4}{(\Delta E_{02}^2 - (\hbar\omega)^2)(\Delta E_{02}^2 - (2\hbar\omega)^2)} \quad (S10)$$

To gain more quantitative insights on the charge-transfer phenomena occurring upon photo-excitation of the azo-derivatives, the amount of charge transferred (q^{CT}), as well as the CT distance (d^{CT} , that is, the spatial extent of the charge delocalization) were evaluated from the difference between the ground- and excited-state electron densities, using the procedure described in Ref.^[68]

Table S 6. Vertical transition wavelength (λ_{02} , nm) and energy (ΔE_{02} , eV), oscillator strength (f_{02} , dimensionless), dipole moment variation ($\Delta\mu_{02}$, D), charge transfer (q^{CT} , |e|), charge transfer distance (d^{CT} , Å), associated with the $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ electronic transition, calculated at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level in chloroform for (*E*)-isomers. The last columns report the static and dynamic hyperpolarizabilities, as well as the dispersion factor, calculated using equations S8-S10.

Compound	λ_{02} (ΔE_{02}) [nm (eV)]	f_{TSA}	$\Delta\mu_{02}$ [D]	q^{CT} [e]	d^{CT} [Å]	$\beta_{HRS,TSA}^{static}$ [u.a.]	$ F(\omega) $	$\beta_{HRS,TSA}^{1300nm}$ [u.a.]
1a	375 (3.30)	1.209	4.28	0.48	1.84	4241	1.6371	6943
1b	363 (3.42)	1.063	3.13	0.48	1.36	2467	1.5752	3886
1c	365 (3.39)	1.087	3.85	0.48	1.97	3163	1.5868	5019
1d	363 (3.42)	1.050	3.51	0.48	1.53	2730	1.5756	4302
1e	369 (3.36)	1.107	4.61	0.49	1.97	3975	1.6048	6380
1f	365 (3.39)	1.032	3.85	0.48	1.66	3002	1.5865	4763
2a	380 (3.26)	1.197	5.79	0.50	2.43	5896	1.6609	9793
2b	365 (3.40)	1.007	4.43	0.49	1.87	3353	1.5848	5315
2c	367 (3.38)	1.069	4.83	0.48	2.09	3945	1.5936	6290
2d	366 (3.39)	1.012	4.54	0.49	1.95	3480	1.5881	5526
2e	373 (3.32)	1.090	5.31	0.49	2.27	4647	1.6239	7548
2f	367 (3.38)	0.996	4.65	0.48	2.01	3538	1.5935	5639
3a	418 (2.96)	1.724	2.07	0.45	0.96	4064	1.9082	7756
3b	409 (3.03)	1.602	0.89	0.44	0.42	1480	1.8385	2721
3c	410 (3.02)	1.610	1.66	0.44	0.78	2866	1.8479	5296
3d	409 (3.03)	1.574	1.24	0.44	0.59	2072	1.8385	3810
3e	412 (3.01)	1.623	2.58	0.45	1.18	4535	1.8575	8424
3f	410 (3.03)	1.567	1.82	0.44	0.86	3028	1.8385	5567

Figure S 188. Correlation between the dynamic ($\lambda = 1300$ nm) β_{HRS} values calculated at the TDDFT level and evaluated using the two-state approximation.

Expressions of the rotational invariants $\langle \beta_{ZZZ}^2 \rangle$ and $\langle \beta_{ZXX}^2 \rangle$ in terms the molecular Cartesian components:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \beta_{ZZZ}^2 \rangle = & \frac{1}{7} \sum_{\zeta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\zeta}^2 + \frac{4}{35} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\eta}^2 + \frac{2}{35} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\zeta} \beta_{\zeta\eta\eta} + \frac{4}{35} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\eta\zeta\zeta} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\eta} \\
 & + \frac{4}{35} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\zeta} \beta_{\eta\eta\zeta} + \frac{1}{35} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\eta\zeta\zeta}^2 + \frac{4}{105} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta \neq \xi}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\eta} \beta_{\eta\xi\xi} \\
 & + \frac{1}{105} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta \neq \xi}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\eta\zeta\zeta} \beta_{\eta\xi\xi} + \frac{4}{105} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta \neq \xi}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\eta} \beta_{\xi\xi\eta} + \frac{2}{105} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta \neq \xi}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\eta\xi}^2 \\
 & + \frac{4}{105} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta \neq \xi}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\eta\xi} \beta_{\eta\zeta\xi}
 \end{aligned} \tag{S11}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \beta_{ZXX}^2 \rangle = & \frac{1}{35} \sum_{\zeta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\zeta}^2 + \frac{8}{105} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\eta}^2 + \frac{4}{105} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\zeta} \beta_{\zeta\eta\eta} - \frac{2}{35} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\eta\zeta\zeta} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\eta} \\
 & - \frac{2}{35} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\zeta} \beta_{\eta\eta\zeta} + \frac{3}{35} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\eta\zeta\zeta}^2 - \frac{2}{105} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta \neq \xi}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\eta} \beta_{\eta\xi\xi} \\
 & + \frac{1}{35} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta \neq \xi}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\eta\zeta\zeta} \beta_{\eta\xi\xi} - \frac{2}{105} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta \neq \xi}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\zeta\eta} \beta_{\xi\xi\eta} + \frac{2}{35} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta \neq \xi}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\eta\xi}^2 \\
 & - \frac{2}{105} \sum_{\zeta \neq \eta \neq \xi}^{x,y,z} \beta_{\zeta\eta\xi} \beta_{\eta\zeta\xi}
 \end{aligned} \tag{S12}$$